

Influence of steric bulk around the vinyl sulfone bond on the reaction patterns of vinyl sulfone-modified carbohydrates. An experimental and theoretical investigation[†]

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Abstract : Steric bulks attached to sulfur atom of vinyl sulfone-modified hex-2-enopyranosides and the anomeric centre control the rate of reactions of these Michael acceptors. Amongst the two, the steric bulk at C-1 is more efficient in retarding the reaction rate of Michael addition reaction. The conformational analysis performed with 2a and 2e using quantum chemical calculations suggests that the addition of isopropylamine would be slower for 2e compared to 2a due to the more steric hindrance in the former case.

Keywords : Vinyl sulfone, carbohydrate, steric bulk, Michael addition.

Introduction

In order to study the influence of the anomeric configuration on the diastereoselectivity of the addition of amines to vinyl sulfone-modified (VSM) hex-2-enopyranosides, we reacted anomerically pure vinyl sulfones **1 α** and **1 β** (Fig. 1) with various primary and secondary amines¹. Primary amines, such as isobutylamine, benzylamine and cyclohexylamine were found to add diastereoselectively to **1 α** to produce single isomers with the D-gluco configuration. The secondary amines, pyrrolidine, piperidine, morpholine and ethyl isonipicotate, on the other hand, generated a mixture (isomeric at C-2) of the D-gluco analogues (major) and D-manno-analogues (minor)¹. The β -anomeric vinyl sulfone **1 β** on reactions with primary as well as secondary amines afforded only β -D-gluco-isomers in all cases. Interestingly, **1 α** did not react with sterically bulky *tert*-butylamine even at an elevated temperature whereas **1 β** reacted smoothly with the same amine at elevated temperature to produce a single D-gluco-isomer in an excellent yield^{1,2}.

Fig. 1. Structures of α and β vinyl sulfone-modified carbohydrates and their amine adducts.

Reactions of *tert*-butylamine exemplified an extreme case of anomeric configuration influencing the addition of nucleophiles to enopyranoside systems **1 α** and **1 β** . The X-ray analysis of the single crystal of methyl 4,6-*O*-benzylidene-2,3-dideoxy-3-*C*-phenylsulfonyl-2-*tert*-butylamino- β -D-glucopyranoside **1 β amino** (Fig. 1) revealed that the pyranose ring assumed a boat conforma-

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tion to facilitate the positioning of the methoxy group of C-1 away from the $N(\text{CH}_3)_3$ group at C-2 (Fig. 1). However, in the case of α -methoxy series **1 α** amino (Fig. 1), any increase in the conformational angle MeO-C1-C2-NR is prohibited because of the axial disposition of C-1 methoxy group. Thus, a bulkier group greater than a critical size, could not be accommodated at the C-2 position of the α -anomers³.

Results and discussion

Since the sterically bulky incoming *tert*-butylamine did not react with the otherwise efficient Michael acceptor **1 α** to furnish the addition product with *tert*-butylamine³, we argued that a perfect combination of the steric bulk attached to the anomeric carbon as well as the same attached to the sulfonyl group, both situated at the γ and γ' positions (Fig. 1) with respect to the reactive α -carbon of **1 α** would be capable of exclusively blocking the reactivity of this Michael acceptor. We also wondered whether it would be possible to deliver a primary amine from the β -face of the pyranose ring by increasing the steric bulk at the anomeric position and/or attached to the sulfonyl group. Therefore, studies on the systems like **2a-e**, **3** and **4** (Scheme 1) have been undertaken under amination reaction conditions.

Reaction Conditions: for compound **6a** (i) NaSMe, MeOH, 65 °C for compounds **6b-e** and **12** (i) DMF, R'SH, TMG, 65 °C, 5h; for compound **9** (i) MeOH, ^tBuSH, TMG, 80-90 °C, 16h (ii) MMPP, MeOH, rt, 6h (iii) MsCl, Py, 0-4 °C, overnight.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of vinyl sulfone-modified carbohydrate.

Following the strategies reported earlier^{1,2}, we synthesized vinyl sulfones **2a-e**, **3** and **4** (Scheme 1). Thus, the known sugar-derived epoxide **5** was reacted with NaSMe in MeOH to afford **6a**. The corresponding sulfone derivative **7a** was generated in quantitative yield by oxidizing **6a** with MMPP (magnesium monoperoxyphthalate hexahydrate) in MeOH. Compound **7a** was subjected to elimination reaction using methanesulfonyl chloride in pyridine at 0 °C to +4 °C to afford **2a** in 93% yield. Similarly, benzylthiol, *p*-tolylthiol, 2-naphthylthiol and *tert*-butylthiol were reacted separately with the same epoxide **5** in DMF in the presence of 1,1,3,3-tetramethylguanidine (TMG) to generate the corresponding sulfide derivatives **6b-e** respectively. Oxidation of compounds **6b-e** to **7b-e** followed by the elimination of the hydroxyl group of latter compounds using methanesulfonyl chloride in pyridine afforded the desired vinyl sulfones **2b-e** in good yields. For the synthesis of the benzyl glycoside analogue **3** and the ethyl glycoside analogue **4** a similar strategy was used starting from epoxides **8** and **11**, respectively (Scheme 1).

Vinyl sulfones **2a-e** on reactions with isopropylamine (5 eq.) in THF (5 mL/mmol) at ambient temperature generated single isomers **14a-e** in high yields (Scheme 2) and the ethyl glycoside **3**, on reactions with isopropylamine, generated a single isomer **15** in high yield in 45 h. The benzyl glycoside **4** was resistant to isopropylamine and the unreacted starting material was recovered even after 36 h at room temperature (Scheme 2).

Reaction conditions: (i) isopropylamine/THF, rt

Scheme 2. Reactions of various vinyl sulfone-modified carbohydrates with isopropylamine.

NMR data of compounds **14a**, **14c-e** and **15** are consistent with the assigned structures. The $J_{1,2}$ values (2.88–3.9 Hz) of compounds **14a**, **14c-e** and **15** are comparable to those of previously reported analogous compounds¹. In all these cases the H-1 signal appeared between δ 4.73–4.92. ¹H NMR data of compound **14b** suggested different values for both H-1 signal as well as $J_{1,2}$. Although, the H-1 signal for **14b** appeared at δ 4.71, the $J_{1,2}$ value of the same compound was found to be < 0.5 Hz. However, the structure of compound **14b** as well as **14d** was unambiguously established as *gluco* derivative by X-ray analysis of their single crystals (Fig. 2).

14b (CCDC 886812)

14d (CCDC 886813)

Fig. 2. ORTEP diagrams of **14b** and **14d**.

Compound **2a** with the smallest steric-bulk on sulfur reacted with amines within 4 h. When the methyl group

(as in **2a**) was substituted with benzyl in **2b**, the reaction was three time slower (12 h). Since **1a** having a phenyl ring attached to sulfur was reported¹ to react smoothly with amines, compound **2c** with comparable steric-bulk also reacted easily with isopropylamine in 8 h. The yields of adducts **14a-c** however, remained comparable. However, a reaction time of 12 h for compound **2b** was indicative of the impact of increasing steric bulk on sulfur of this class of compounds on the reaction pattern. The 2-naphthyl and the *tert*-butyl group on sulfur drastically slowed down the reaction by increasing the reaction time to 26 and 34 h, respectively. Interestingly, there are scattered reports on the influence of various groups attached to sulfur of vinyl sulfone group. For example, it was reported that the rates of addition of 2'-(phenethyl)thiol to different vinyl sulfonyl Michael acceptors vary over 3 orders of magnitude, with phenyl vinyl sulfonate esters being *ca.* 3000-fold more reactive than *N*-benzyl vinyl sulfonamides⁴. On the other hand, alkyl groups (R) in $-\text{CH}=\text{CHS}(\text{O})_2\text{-R}$ systems reportedly shielded the β -carbons "through space" in the order : *t*-Bu > *i*-Pr > Et in acyclic systems⁵. The latter observation appears to be applicable and similar to the reaction patterns of cyclic systems like VSM pyranosides **2a-e** as evident from our results.

In our case, however the matter was further complicated by the anomeric configuration and steric bulk of the anomeric alkoxy groups. In order to examine the effect of steric bulk attached to the anomeric carbon, the higher homologue of **2e**, namely the vinyl sulfone-modified ethyl glycoside **3** was reacted with isopropylamine under the conditions stated above (Scheme 2). In line with our expectations, the increase in the steric bulk attached to the anomeric center from methyl- (as in **2e**) to ethyl- (as in **3**) drastically reduced the reactivity of vinyl sulfones group as evident from the long reaction time of 45 h. Finally, the sterically bulkier benzyloxy group of the benzyl glycoside **4** manifested an extreme influence of steric bulk by blocking completely the reactivity of the C-2 centre (Scheme 2).

Computational studies : Experimental observations suggest that the rate of reaction of vinyl sulfones-modified hex-2-enopyranosides with isopropylamine is influenced by the steric bulk of the substituents attached to the sulfur atom. To examine the experimental findings, com-

putational study has been performed using quantum chemical calculations. For computational study, we have considered **2a** ($R = R' = \text{Me}$) and **2e** ($R = \text{Me}$, $R' = t\text{-Bu}$) as representative systems from less steric bulk to relatively larger systems attached to the sulfur atom, respectively. The reaction time for **2a** with isopropylamine is 4 h, whereas in the case of **2e** the reaction time is 34 h. In our previous report⁶, we have shown that the addition of amine to VSM carbohydrates proceeds through a concerted mechanism, in which $\text{N}\cdots\text{C}$ bond formation and proton transfer takes place simultaneously. Further, it was mentioned that the equatorial approach of isopropylamine towards the VSM carbohydrates was preferred to the axial approach⁶.

In this study, RHF/6-31G* calculated⁷ that the equatorial face of **2e** was highly hindered than that of **2a** due to *t*-butyl group. The space-filled models depict nicely the more hindered olefinic site of **2e** compared to **2a** (**2e-1**, Fig. 3). The approach of isopropylamine to the olefinic site of **2e** requires the $-\text{SO}_2(t\text{-Bu})$ group to rotate away for better approach of the reagent. The barrier for rotation along the C2-S3 bond (Fig. 3) was calculated by

constructing one-dimensional potential energy surface at RHF/6-31G* level of theory. To construct the potential energy surface the C2-S3 bond was allowed to rotate to 360° with an increment of 10° . The conformer of **2e** with C1-C2-S3-C4 dihedral angle 96.2° (**2e-1**) was considered as a starting point as this conformer was found to be the lowest energy conformer on potential energy surface (Fig. 4). The conformer **2e-2** obtained with the torsional value (δ C1-C2-S3-C4 = 1.5°) is 11.1 kcal/mol higher in energy than **2e-1** on the potential energy surface (Figs. 3 and 4). This conformer shows the open face of the olefinic double bond to be attacked by isopropylamine. However, in conformer **2e-2**, the equatorial face of olefinic site is sufficiently open for the approach of isopropylamine (Fig. 3). Similar potential energy surface constructed for **2a** showed that **2a-1** as the stable conformer (δ C1-C2-S3-C4 = 75.7°), whereas, the even more open conformer corresponds to **2e-2** (**2a-2**, δ C1-C2-S3-C4 = 4.8°) is 8.9 kcal/mol higher in energy than the **2a-1**. These calculated results indicate that the addition reaction of isopropylamine would be faster with **2a** than **2e**.

Fig. 3. RHF/6-31G* calculated more stable conformers of **2a** and **2e** (**2a-1** and **2e-1**), and their corresponding higher energy conformers (**2a-2** and **2e-2**). Both space-filled and tube models are given for clarity purpose [gray = carbon; red = oxygen; yellow = sulfur; white = hydrogen].

Fig. 4. RHF/6-31G* calculated one dimensional potential energy surface of (a) **2e** and (b) **2a**.

Conclusion

The changing reaction patterns of **2a-e** with isopropylamine clearly established that the steric bulk attached to sulfur is directly related to the rate of reactions of vinyl sulfones-modified hex-2-enopyranosides. We have also established that sterically bulky group attached to the anomeric carbon also blocked the C-2 site. However, it appeared from the reaction patterns of **2b** and **4** that the blocking effect of the steric bulk attached to anomeric position is more dominating than the bulk attached to sulfur in terms of blocking the C-2 position but this domination did not lead to the attack of the amine at C-2 from the β -face. These RHF calculated results suggest that the steric hindrance and the higher rotational barrier in the case of **2e** would reduce the approach of isopropylamine compared to the case of **2a**. Earlier, the diastereoselectivity of addition of nucleophiles to 1α and 1β was discussed in terms of electrostatic interaction, stereoelectronic con-

trol, steric hindrance, $A^{1,3}$ strain and also hydrogen bonding¹. More recently, we established that the protecting groups of vinyl sulfones-modified hex-2-enopyranosides present at C-6 and C-4 play an important role in determining the rate and the selectivity of addition of amines to these compounds⁶. The present study emphasizes that henceforth, any discussion on the selectivity of addition of nucleophiles to electron deficient hex-2-enopyranosyl systems would require the study of the influence of steric bulk around the vinyl sulfones group as well.

Experimental

General methods : All reactions were conducted under N_2 atmosphere. Melting points were determined in open-end capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Carbohydrates and other fine chemicals were obtained from commercial suppliers and are used without purification. Solvents were dried and distilled following the standard procedures. TLC was carried out on pre-coated plates (Merck silica gel 60, f_{254}) and the spots were visualized with UV light or by charring the plate dipped in 5% H_2SO_4 -MeOH solution. Column chromatography was performed on silica gel (230-400 mesh). 1H and ^{13}C NMR for most of the compounds were recorded at 200/400 and 50/100 MHz, respectively using $CDCl_3$ as the solvent unless stated otherwise. DEPT 135 experiments have been carried out to identify the methylene carbons. Optical rotations were recorded at 589 nm. High Resolution Mass Spectra were recorded on an Electrospray-Ionisation Mass Spectrometer.

General procedure for the synthesis of compounds 2a-e, 3 and 4 : To a solution of **5**, **8** and **11** (1 eq.) in DMF (5 mL/mmol) were added thiols (5 eq.) and TMG (3 eq.). In the case of **6a**, NaSMe (2.5 eq.) was used and the reaction was carried out in MeOH (20 mL). The reaction mixture was heated under N_2 for 6-12 h at 80-90 °C, cooled to room temperature and poured into satd. aq. NaCl solution (80 mL). The mixture was extracted with EtOAc (3 \times 30 mL). The EtOAc layer was washed with satd. aq. $NaHCO_3$ (2 \times 25 mL). EtOAc layers were pooled together, dried over anhyd. Na_2SO_4 , filtered and the filtrate was evaporated under reduced pressure. The resulting residues were purified over silica gel to yield **6a-e**, **9** and **12**, respectively. To the separate solutions of **6a-e**, **9** and **12** (1 eq.) in MeOH (30 mL) was added

MMPP (3–4 eq.). The reaction mixture was stirred for 6 h at room temperature and filtered. The filtrate was evaporated under reduced pressure and the residues were neutralized with satd. aq. NaHCO_3 (70 mL). The organic layer was separated and dried over anhyd. Na_2SO_4 , filtered and the filtrate was concentrated to dryness under reduced pressure and purified through a short column of silica gel to yield **7a-e**, **10** and **13**. To the separate solutions of **7a-e**, **10** and **13** (1 eq.) in dry pyridine (5 mL/mmol) was added a solution of methanesulfonyl chloride (3 eq.) in dry pyridine (2 mL/mmol) at 0 °C. The mixture was left overnight at 4 °C, poured into satd. aq. NaHCO_3 (70 mL) and the aqueous phase was extracted with EtOAc (3 × 30 mL). Organic layers were pooled together, dried over anhyd. Na_2SO_4 , filtered and the filtrate was evaporated to dryness. To the crude residue thus obtained, was added dry pyridine (20 mL) and the resulting solution was heated under reflux for 0.5–2 h. Pyridine was evaporated under reduced pressure to get an oily residue. The resulting residues were purified over silica gel to yield **2a-e**, **3** and **4** respectively.

Methyl 2,3-dideoxy-4,6-di-O-(phenylmethylene)-3-C-methylsulfonyl-β-D-erythro-hex-2-enopyranoside (2a): Following the general procedure, **7a** (0.62 g, 2.31 mmol) afforded **2a** (0.54 g, 93%); [Eluent : EtOAc : pet ether (1 : 3)], white solid, m.p. 132–134 °C; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{28}$: -53.4 (c 0.75, CHCl_3); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 3.04 (3H, s), 3.51 (3H, s), 3.84–4.08 (2H, m), 4.34–4.41 (1H, m), 4.59–4.63 (1H, m), 5.09–5.10 (1H, m), 5.68 (1H, s), 6.81–6.83 (1H, m), 7.35–7.49 (5H, m); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$: δ 43.8, 56.5, 63.7, 68.6 (CH_2), 73.7, 95.2, 101.9, 125.9, 128.2, 129.1, 135.5, 136.5, 141.2. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_6\text{S}$: C, 55.20; H, 5.56. Found : C, 55.20; H, 5.32.

Methyl 2,3-dideoxy-4,6-di-O-(phenylmethylene)-3-C-benzylsulfonyl-α-D-erythro-hex-2-enopyranoside (2b): Following the general procedure, **7b** (0.62 g, 2.31 mmol) afforded **2b** (0.54 g, 90%); [Eluent : EtOAc : pet ether (1 : 3)], white solid, m.p. 123–125 °C; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{28}$: -42.1 (c 0.75, CHCl_3); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 3.42 (3H, s), 3.51 (3H, s), 3.89–4.04 (2H, m), 4.34–4.47 (3H, m), 4.64–4.66 (1H, m), 4.98 (1H, s), 5.75 (1H, s), 6.49 (1H, m), 7.32–7.41 (8H, m), 7.55–7.57 (2H, m); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$: δ 56.6, 61.9 (CH_2), 63.9, 68.9 (CH_2), 74.1, 95.4, 102.3, 126.1, 127.4, 128.4, 128.6, 128.9, 129.4, 131.1, 136.7, 137.9, 139.2. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_6\text{S}$: C, 62.67; H, 5.51. Found : C, 62.40; H, 5.82.

Methyl 2,3-dideoxy-4,6-di-O-(phenylmethylene)-3-C-(2-naphthyl)sulfonyl-β-D-erythro-hex-2-enopyranoside (2d): Following the general procedure for the synthesis of **2a-b**, compound **5** (0.65 g, 2.33 mmol) afforded **7d**. After usual workup and without any further purification, following the general procedure **7d** was converted to **2d** (0.57 g, 89%); [Eluent : EtOAc : pet ether (1 : 4)], white solid, m.p. 128–130 °C; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{28}$: -39.4 (c 0.75, CHCl_3); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 3.49 (3H, s), 3.77–3.86 (2H, m), 4.22 (1H, d, J 6.0 Hz), 4.57 (1H, d, J 6.4 Hz), 5.14 (1H, s), 5.53 (1H, s), 6.95–7.01 (5H, m), 7.23–7.24 (2H, m), 7.49–7.82 (5H, m), 7.84–7.86 (1H, m), 8.36 (1H, s); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$: δ 56.6, 63.8, 63.9, 68.8 (CH_2), 74.1, 95.6, 102.2, 123.2, 126.1, 127.1, 127.7, 127.9, 128.8, 129.0, 129.6, 130.8, 131.9, 135.1, 135.4, 136.3, 136.8, 142.3. HRMS (ES, $(\text{M}+\text{H})^+$) : for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{23}\text{O}_6\text{S}$ Calcd. 439.1215, found 439.1212.

*Methyl 2,3-dideoxy-4,6-di-O-(phenylmethylene)-3-C-*t*-butylsulfonyl-α-D-erythro-hex-2-enopyranoside (2e)*: Following the general procedure, **7e** (0.65 g, 2.33 mmol) afforded **2e** (0.51 g, 86%); [Eluent : EtOAc : pet ether (1 : 4)], white solid. m.p. 136–138 °C; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{28}$: -58.2 (c 0.75, CHCl_3); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 1.33 (9H, s), 3.48 (3H, s), 3.81–4.04 (2H, m), 4.35 (1H, dd), 4.51–4.55 (1H, m), 4.06 (1H, m), 5.63 (1H, s), 6.75 (1H, t), 7.32–7.50 (5H, m); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$: δ 23.8 (3 × CH_3), 56.3, 60.8, 63.9, 68.6 (CH_2), 73.9, 95.1, 102.0, 126.0, 127.9, 128.8, 136.6, 140.1, 140.8. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_6\text{S}$: C, 58.68; H, 6.57. Found : C, 58.54; H, 6.63.

*Ethyl 2,3-dideoxy-4,6-di-O-(phenylmethylene)-3-C-*t*-butylsulfonyl-α-D-erythro-hex-2-enopyranoside (3)*: Following the general procedure, **10** (0.39 g, 1.63 mmol) afforded **3** (0.51 g, 84%); [Eluent : EtOAc : pet ether (1 : 4)], white solid, m.p. 115–116 °C; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{28}$: -34.6 (c 0.625, CDCl_3); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 0.95–1.29 (3H, m), 1.31 (9H, s), 3.57–4.13 (4H, m), 4.30–4.34 (1H, m), 4.50–4.55 (1H, m), 5.19 (1H, s), 5.63 (1H, s), 6.79 (1H, m), 7.17–7.50 (5H, m); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$: δ 15.2, 24.0 (3 × CH_3), 61.0, 64.0 (CH_2), 65.0, 68.9 (CH_2), 74.1, 94.1, 102.2, 126.1, 128.0, 128.9, 136.7, 140.1, 141.4. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_6\text{S}$: C, 59.67; H, 6.85. Found : C, 59.67; H, 6.85.

Benzyl 2,3-dideoxy-4,6-di-O-(phenylmethylene)-3-C-methylsulfonyl-α-D-erythro-hex-2-enopyranoside (4): Following the general procedure, **13** (0.39 g, 1.63 mmol) afforded **4** (0.51 g, 91%); [Eluent : EtOAc : pet ether (1 :

3)], white solid, m.p. 153–154 °C; $[\alpha]_D^{28}$: -50.9 (*c* 0.75, CHCl₃); ¹H NMR : δ 3.04 (3H, s), 3.87–3.92 (1H, m), 4.09–4.12 (1H, m), 4.25–4.32 (1H, m), 4.59–4.86 (3H, m), 5.28–5.29 (1H, m), 5.68 (1H, s), 6.82–6.84 (1H, m), 7.27–7.48 (10H, m); ¹³C NMR : δ 44.1, 64.1, 68.8 (CH₂), 71.1 (CH₂), 74.0, 93.6, 102.2, 126.0, 128.2, 128.3, 128.4, 128.7, 129.3, 135.9, 136.7, 136.8, 141.5. Anal. Calcd. for C₂₁H₂₂O₆S : C, 62.67; H, 5.51. Found : C, 62.91; H, 5.59.

General procedure for the addition of isopropylamine to (2a-e), (3) and (4) : To a solution of **2a-e**, **3**, or **4** in dry THF (5 mL/mmol) was added isopropylamine (5 eq.) and the solutions were stirred at room temperature. After completion of the reaction (TLC), THF was evaporated under reduced pressure. The residues thus obtained were dissolved separately in EtOAc (30 mL) and the organic layers was washed with satd. aq. solution of NaHCO₃ (3 × 30 mL). The organic layer was separated, dried over anhyd. Na₂SO₄, filtered and the filtrates were evaporated under reduced pressure. The residues were purified over silica gel to get the product.

Methyl 2,3-dideoxy-2-C-isopropylamino-3-C-methylsulfonyl-4,6-O-(phenylmethylene)-α-D-glucopyranoside (14a) : Following the general procedure, isopropylamine was reacted with **2a** (0.5 g, 1.28 mmol) for 4 h at room temperature to get **14a** (0.51 g, 91%); [Eluent : EtOAc : pet ether (1 : 3)], white solid, m.p. 159–161 °C; $[\alpha]_D^{28}$: +34.6 (*c* 0.625, CDCl₃); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 1.02–1.26 (6H, m), 2.91–3.05 (1H, m), 3.09 (3H, s), 3.09–3.43 (1H, m), 3.46 (3H, s), 3.72–4.06 (4H, m), 4.26–4.33 (1H, m), 4.76 (1H, d, *J* 3.3 Hz), 5.60 (1H, s), 7.27–7.46 (5H, m); ¹³C NMR : δ 22.3, 24.4, 46.3, 47.0, 54.8, 55.3, 62.2, 63.6, 69.2 (CH₂), 76.0, 98.3, 101.6, 125.9, 128.6, 129.1, 136.7. Anal. Calcd. for C₁₈H₂₇NO₆S : C, 56.09; H, 7.06, N, 3.63. Found : C, 56.05; H, 6.79, N, 3.56.

Methyl 2,3-dideoxy-2-C-isopropylamino-3-C-benzylsulfonyl-4,6-O-(phenylmethylene)-α-D-glucopyranoside (14b) : Following the general procedure, isopropylamine was reacted with **2b** (0.5 g, 1.21 mmol) for 12 h at room temperature to get **14b** (0.55 g, 94%); [Eluent : EtOAc : pet ether (1 : 3)], white solid, m.p. 147–149 °C; $[\alpha]_D^{28}$: +59.7 (*c* 0.75, CDCl₃); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 1.04–1.10 (6H, m), 2.85–2.91 (1H, m), 3.42 (3H, s), 3.45–3.50 (2H, m), 3.77–3.93 (2H, m), 4.07–

4.12 (1H, m), 4.29–4.37 (2H, m), 4.57–4.60 (1H, m), 4.71 (1H, s), 5.65 (1H, s), 7.31–7.52 (10H, m); ¹³C NMR : δ 22.3, 24.4, 47.0, 54.8, 55.3, 60.4, 62.1, 63.7 (CH₂), 69.3 (CH₂), 76.4, 98.4, 101.9, 126.0, 127.2 (C), 128.4, 128.7, 129.2, 131.3, 136.7 (C). Anal. Calcd. for C₂₄H₃₁NO₆S : C, 62.45; H, 6.77, N, 3.03. Found : C, 62.33; H, 6.39, N, 3.07.

Methyl 2,3-dideoxy-2-C-isopropylamino-3-C-(2-naphthyl)sulfonyl-4,6-O-(phenylmethylene)-α-D-glucopyranoside (14d) : Following the general procedure, isopropylamine was reacted with **2d** (0.74 g, 1.84 mmol) at room temperature for 26 h to yield **14d** (0.71 g, 86%); [Eluent : EtOAc : pet ether (1 : 3)], white solid, m.p. 115–116 °C; $[\alpha]_D^{28}$: +31.9 (*c* 0.625, CDCl₃); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 1.08–1.16 (6H, m), 2.99–3.03 (1H, m), 3.43 (3H, s), 3.61–3.73 (2H, m), 3.77–3.84 (2H, m), 3.95–4.01 (1H, m), 4.16–4.19 (1H, m), 4.76 (1H, d, *J* 3.0 Hz), 5.25 (1H, s), 6.74–7.11 (5H, m), 7.48–7.58 (2H, m), 7.77–7.64 (4H, m), 8.35 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR : δ 22.0, 24.2, 47.0, 55.0, 55.3, 62.2, 64.8, 69.2 (CH₂), 76.4, 98.6, 101.3, 123.0, 125.6, 127.2, 127.6, 127.8, 128.7, 129.2, 129.5, 131.9, 135.0, 135.9. HRMS (ES, (M+H)⁺) : for C₂₇H₃₂NO₆S Calcd. 498.1950, found 498.1946.

Methyl 2,3-dideoxy-2-C-isopropylamino-3-C-t-butylsulfonyl-4,6-O-(phenylmethylene)-α-D-glucopyranoside (14e) : Following the general procedure, isopropylamine was reacted with **2e** (0.6 g, 1.28 mmol) for 34 h at room temperature to get compound **14e** (0.52 g, 96%); [Eluent : EtOAc : pet ether (1 : 4)], white solid, m.p. 145–147 °C; $[\alpha]_D^{28}$: +31.5 (*c* 0.625, CHCl₃), m.p. 127–130 °C; $[\alpha]_D^{28}$: +43.4 (*c* 0.625, CDCl₃); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 1.03 (3H, d, *J* 6.4 Hz), 1.05 (3H, d, *J* 6.4 Hz), 2.94–3.01 (1H, m), 3.34–3.38 (1H, m), 3.43 (3H, s), 3.49–3.57 (1H, m), 3.76–3.81 (1H, m), 3.86–3.91 (1H, m), 3.99–4.04 (1H, m), 4.30 (1H, dd, *J* 4.4 Hz), 4.81 (3H, d, *J* 4.0 Hz), 5.59 (1H, s), 7.32–7.36 (3H, m), 7.44–7.46 (2H, m); ¹³C NMR : δ 22.6, 23.6 (3 × CH₃), 24.7, 46.8, 53.8, 55.0, 60.3, 60.6, 62.3 (C), 69.3 (CH₂), 75.1, 98.9, 101.6, 126.0, 127.9, 128.7, 137.0 (C). Anal. Calcd. for C₂₁H₃₃NO₆S : C, 58.99; H, 7.78, N, 3.28. Found : C, 59.39; H, 7.84, N, 3.30.

Ethyl 2,3-dideoxy-2-C-isopropylamino-4,6-O-(phenylmethylene)-3-C-t-butylsulfonyl-α-D-glucopyranoside (15) : Following the general procedure, isopropylamine was reacted with **3** (0.52 g, 1.22 mmol)

for 45 h at room temperature to get **15** (0.49 g, 83%); [Eluent : EtOAc : pet ether (1 : 3)], white solid, m.p. 126–127 °C; $[\alpha]_D^{28} +24.6$ (c 0.625, CDCl_3); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) : δ 0.99–1.04 (6H, m), 1.23–1.27 (3H, m), 1.37 (9H, s), 2.92–3.03 (1H, m), 3.33–3.57 (3H, m), 3.72–4.01 (4H, m), 4.24–4.31 (1H, m), 4.92 (1H, d, J 4.0 Hz), 5.59 (1H, s), 7.30–7.46 (5H, m); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$: δ 14.8, 22.9, 23.7 (3 \times CH_3), 24.7, 47.0, 53.7, 60.4, 60.6, 62.3 (C), 63.4 (CH_2), 69.3 (CH_2), 75.1, 97.8, 101.4, 125.9, 127.9, 128.7, 137.1 (C). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{35}\text{NO}_6\text{S}$: C, 59.84; H, 7.99; N, 3.17. Found : C, 60.04; H, 7.71; N, 3.08.

Computational methods : **2a-1** and **2e-2** were fully optimized with Restricted Hartree-Fock method using 6-31G* basis set⁷. Complete vibrational analyses were performed to characterize the ground state geometries. The one-dimensional potential energy surfaces were constructed by varying the C1-C2-S3-C4 torsional angle for rotation of 360° with increments of 10° in the gas phase using RHF/6-31G* level of theory. All calculations were performed with Gaussian 09 suite program⁸.

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9. CCDC 886812 (**14b**) and CCDC 886813 (**14d**) contain the Supplementary Crystallographic Data for this paper. These data can be obtained free of charge from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data_request/cif.